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Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Manganese(II) Complexes with Bifunctional Tridentate Schiff Bases and Neutral Monodentate Ligands

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In continuation of our work¹ on studies of Schiff base compounds of transition metals, we report here the effect of different monodentate ligands upon the mode of coordination of bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases, thiosemicarbazones of salicylaldehyde (saltsc), benzoin (benzts) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (naptsc) with Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Mn²⁺.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of complexes¹: To a weighed amount of NiCl₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O or MnCl₂·4H₂O was added salicylaldehyde/benzoin/2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in 1:1 molar ratio in ethanolic medium and stirred for 5–10 min in a magnetic stirrer. To it was added pyridine (py), γ -picoline (γ -pic), isoquinoline (iq) or hot ethanolic solution of thiourea (tu) in excess with constant stirring. The resulting complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight, conductance, magnetic, electronic and ir spectral data.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Table 1) are consistent with the formulation of the compounds. The conductance (in nitrobenzene) data (0.31–3.4 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) show that the compounds are non-electrolytes. The molecular weight measurement indicates that the compounds are monomeric.

The infrared spectra (nujol) of the Schiff bases show a broad and strong band at 3 200–2 800 cm^{-1} attributable to ν_{OH} and ν_{NH} modes. It disappears in the spectra of the metal complexes indicating the deprotonation of the ligands. The ν_{C-N} band of the Schiff bases appearing at 1 600 $\pm$ 5 cm^{-1} shifted to 1 620–1 630 cm^{-1} on complexation indicating their coordination through azomethine nitrogen. Bands due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=S}$ modes of the Schiff bases were observed at 1 680 and 1 020 cm^{-1} , respectively. These bands disappear in the complexes indicating the thioenolisation of these ligands and their chelation through thiolic sulphur. This is further supported by appearance of bands at $\sim$ 1 380 (C–O) and $\sim$ 661 cm^{-1} (C–S). Thus the Schiff bases behave as bifunctional tridentate (O, N, S) ligands². The presence of coordinated nitrogen donor ligands, viz. pyridine, γ -picoline and isoquinoline, in the complexes were known from their $\nu_{C-C} + \nu_{C-N}$ bands found at 1 530–1 540 cm^{-1} , although the other band at $\sim$ 1 620 cm^{-1} was masked by the Schiff base band. In the compounds containing thiourea, the ν_{C-S} band of free thiourea shifted to lower frequency at 710–720 cm^{-1} indicating its coordination through the sulphur atom. Further the bands of the compounds observed in the far-infrared region at 420–440 and 610–625 cm^{-1} may be due to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O} modes, respectively³.

The μ_{eff} values (3.7–4.1 B.M.) of the three blue Ni²⁺ complexes (sl. nos. 1, 2 and 3; Table 1) and absorption band at 14 925–15 873 cm^{-1} due to ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ transition suggest tetrahedral geometry for these complexes. The two brown complexes (sl. nos. 4 and 5; Table 1) showed bands at 11 904–12 121, 16 129–16 806 and 27 777–28 985 cm^{-1} due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively, which

TABLE I - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no	Compd.*	M.p. °C	Mol. wt Found/(Calcd)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} ** B.M.
				Metal	S	
1.	Ni(Napt-c)(py)	199	360.41 (382.89)	15.12 (15.33)	8.02 (8.4)	4.1
2.	Ni(Naptsc)(γ -pic)	240	300.00 (396.96)	14.42 (14.78)	7.83 (8.1)	3.83
3.	Ni(Benzts)(γ -pic)	250	435.32 (431.02)	13.23 (13.61)	7.05 (7.4)	3.72
4.	Ni(Benzts)(tu) ₂	205	540.0 (571.95)	10.11 (10.26)	22.23 (22.4)	3.4
5.	Ni(Salts)(tu) ₂	185	401.0 (481.7)	12.02 (12.18)	26.21 (26.6)	3.28
6.	Cu(Naptsc)(py) ₂	210	400.0 (466.69)	13.25 (13.60)	6.42 (6.87)	2.2
7.	Cu(Naptsc)(γ -pic) ₂	172	400.0 (496.83)	12.41 (12.78)	6.21 (6.4)	2.1
8.	Cu(Benzts)(py) ₂	290	566.00 (506.75)	12.12 (12.53)	6.13 (6.3)	2.03
9.	Cu(Salts)(py) ₂	265	400.00 (416.5)	15.02 (15.24)	7.42 (7.7)	1.95
10.	Cu(Salts)(γ -pic) ₂	165	466.6 (444.64)	14.06 (14.28)	7.12 (7.2)	2.03
11.	Cu(Naptsc)(tu) ₂	141	567.9 (536.69)	11.54 (11.83)	22.11 (22.2)	1.89
12.	Cu(Benzts)(tu) ₂	110	500.0 (576.75)	10.98 (11.01)	22.02 (22.2)	1.75
13.	Cu(Salts)(tu) ₂	160	400.0 (486.5)	13.03 (13.15)	26.05 (26.3)	1.9
14.	Mn(Naptsc)(py)	250	400.0 (379.13)	14.24 (14.49)	8.23 (8.4)	5.92
15.	Mn(Naptsc)(γ -pic)	250	367.0 (393.20)	13.58 (14.01)	7.81 (8.1)	5.82
16.	Mn(Benzts)(py)	250	400.0 (419.19)	12.92 (13.10)	7.52 (7.6)	5.7
17.	Mn(Benzts)(γ -pic)	250	367.0 (433.29)	12.38 (12.68)	7.23 (7.4)	5.9

*Salts: C₉H₇N₃OS; Naptsc: C₁₂H₉N₃OS; Benzts: C₁₅H₁₃N₃OS. **Gouy method.

are consistent with the octahedral Ni²⁺ stereochemistry. This is further supported by μ_{eff} values of 3.23-3.40 B.M. The blue Cu²⁺ complexes (sl. nos. 6-8; Table I) showed normal μ_{eff} values (1.75-2.2 B.M.). They showed absorption band at 15748-16666 cm⁻¹ as observed with five-coordinate complexes of copper⁷⁻⁹. A broad band at 15625-15873 cm⁻¹ due to ³E_g → ³T_{2g} transition in the spectra of the yellow-green Cu²⁺ complexes (sl. nos. 11-13; Table I) suggests distorted octahedral configuration¹⁰. The yellow-pink Mn²⁺ complexes (sl. nos. 14-17; Table I) showed bands

at 20833-22471, 23255-25316 and 26315-27777 cm⁻¹ due to ⁶A₁ → ⁶T₁(G), ⁶A₁ → ⁴T₂(G) and ⁶A₁ → ⁴E, ⁴A₁(G) transitions respectively, which are consistent with the value of tetrahedrally coordinated^{11,12} manganese(II). The μ_{eff} values (5.78-5.95 B.M.) are consistent with high-spin d⁵-configuration.

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Structural and Biocidal Studies of Ternary Complexes of some Transition Metals

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THE paper reports the isolation, characterisation and fungicidal activity of the mixed ligand complexes (MLL') of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} with *N*-pyridylanthranilic acid, Npa(L), 2-picolinic acid, PIC, and 2-furoic acid, FA(L').

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The metal acetate solution (0.01M in 30 ml water)

was treated with a mixture of Npa² and PIC or FA (each 0.01M in 70 ml methanol). The mixture was brought to pH 5.0–6.6 by adding 1% alcoholic ammonia solution and refluxed for 2.5 h. The resulting solid complexes were filtered washed with

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/Calcd		μ_{eff}
	N	M	
Cu(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	9.87 (10.08)	15.12 (15.24)	1.92
Ni(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	10.15 (10.20)	14.15 (14.25)	3.26
Co(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	10.05 (10.19)	14.22 (14.29)	4.98
Cu(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	6.85 (6.90)	15.45 (15.66)	2.11
Ni(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	6.82 (6.99)	14.48 (14.64)	3.31
Co(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	6.89 (6.98)	14.53 (14.68)	5.07

methanol and ether, dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 . The elemental analysis of the metal complexes (Table 1) indicate 1 : 1 : 1 (MLL') type stoichiometry.

The molar conductance (in DMF), magnetic moments (at room temperature), ir and electronic (in DMF) spectra of the complexes were explored for their characterisation. The ligands and their metal complexes were screened² for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *A. flavus* and *Penicillium citrinum* in agar culture media (Table 2) at 37° for 96 h.

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductance values ($1.3-3.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) suggest non-electrolytic nature of all the complexes. The solid complexes do not possess sharp melting point but decompose on heating at 200–250°.

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF LIGAND COMPLEXES

Compd.	% Inhibition at concentration (ppm) level								
	<i>A. niger</i>			<i>A. flavus</i>			<i>P. citrinum</i>		
	100	200	500	100	200	500	100	200	500
PIC	45.4	55.5	98.8	43.7	57.6	87.2	40.7	46.9	91.2
FA	38.6	45.3	85.7	33.4	49.5	78.2	32.4	40.3	85.6
Npa	56.8	68.0	70.3	65.5	72.8	75.7	60.2	69.3	74.4
Cu(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	65.8	79.6	—	75.3	83.7	93.4	72.4	81.8	98.3
Ni(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	71.3	85.4	—	79.4	89.2	—	78.3	88.4	—
Co(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	75.9	90.4	—	86.5	95.3	—	83.5	92.1	—
Cu(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	68.4	82.5	92.3	80.2	86.1	96.8	70.3	80.5	96.1
Ni(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	72.4	85.6	98.9	83.7	89.5	—	74.8	84.1	—
Co(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	77.3	88.0	—	88.5	93.6	—	79.1	88.2	—